

REVIEW ON ALZHEIMER W.S.R TO CHIKITSA (RASAYAN)***¹Vd. Chitra Karekar, ²Vd. Vinodini Payghan, ³Vd. Vipin Atram**¹Associate Professor, Department of Kayachikitsa. Bhusaheb Mulak Ayurved Medical College Hospital Research.²Associate Professor, Department of Roagnidan and Vitkruti Vijayan Bhusaheb Mulak Ayurved Medical College Hospital Research.³Associate Professor, Shalya Tantra, Department of SRK Ayurved College and Hospital, Bhopal.***Corresponding Author: Vd. Chitra Karekar**Associate Professor, Department of Kayachikitsa. Bhusaheb Mulak Ayurved Medical College Hospital Research. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18480564>**How to cite this Article:** *¹Vd. Chitra Karekar, ²Vd. Vinodini Payghan, ³Vd. Vipin Atram (2026). Review On Alzheimer W.S.R To Chikitsa (Rasayan). World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(2), 458–460.

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ABSTRACT

The central nervous system, which is made up of the brain, spinal cord, and other major organs, is the principal organ of the human body. The most prevalent type of dementia, Alzheimer's disease, is a neurological ailment that affects the older population and progresses irreversibly. By 2030, there will be approximately 1 billion people on the planet, up from 420 million in 2000, and with an increase in the percentage of elderly people from 7% to 12%. The cause of AD is yet unknown. The pathophysiology of AD includes low levels of the neurotransmitter Ach, aggregation of the amyloid beta peptide, accumulation of hyperphosphorylated tau protein, dyshomeostasis of biometals, oxidative stress, mitochondrial dysfunction, and neuroinflammation. The slow and steady decline in memory that affects language, personality, or cognitive control is the result of all these variables. There is no reliable diagnostic procedure; a brain autopsy is the only way to make a conclusive diagnosis of AD. The review indicates that Ayurvedic drugs like Brahmi, Mandookaparni, Shankhapushpi, Jyotishmati, Ashwagandha, Jatamansi, Madhuyashti, and Guduchi have the potential to provide a significant improvement in the memory and learning capacity of the elderly suffering from AD. All these drugs improve the brain functions and also the sensory and motor systems as a result of their medhyaproperties and thereby can help in the management of various cognitive disorders, mainly AD.

KEYWORDS: Rasayan, Alzheimer's disease, Herbal medicine.**INTRODUCTION**

Alzheimer's disease is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder in which a gradual memory decline, along with a loss of one area of higher intellectual function, is involved. The domains affected are cognition, daily functioning, and behaviour. The cognition includes memory orientation and judgment. Alzheimer's disease is the most common form of dementia among middle-aged and older adults. Although AD develops differently for every individual, there are many common symptoms. Early symptoms are often mistakenly thought to be 'age-related' concerns or manifestations of stress. In the early stages, the most common symptom is difficulty remembering recent events, known as short-term memory loss. When AD is suspected, the diagnosis is usually confirmed with tests that evaluate behaviour and thinking abilities, often followed by a brain scan if available; however, examination of brain tissue is

required for a definitive diagnosis. As the disease advances, symptoms can include confusion, irritability, aggression, mood swings, trouble with language, and long-term memory loss. As the person's condition declines, they often withdraw from family and society. Gradually, bodily functions are lost, ultimately leading to death.

OBJECTIVES

1. To analyse and understand Alzheimer's disease from an Ayurvedic perspective.
2. To review the Ayurvedic herbs acting on Alzheimer's disease.

METHODS

Literary sources: All major textbooks of Ayurveda were used for a literary survey, and different websites and

various journal references were analysed and used for the study.

Four folds of Rasayana

- 1) Maintenance of Positive Health
- 2) Improvement of 3 mental Faculties Dhee- Dhruthi - Smruti
- 3) Resistance against Disease
- 4) Longevity

Tridosha and Cognitive Functions

Doshas play a vital role in maintaining cognitive functions. Any factors that impair the shareerika bhava's (physical factors) will also affect the Manasika bhava's (mental factors). Vata regulates the proper functioning of the Buddhi (intellect), Indriya (cognitive and motor organs), and Manah (psyche). While pitta (body humour) enhances Medha (intellect) and Kapha (body humour) nurtures dhee (intelligence), dhriti (fortitude), and smriti (memory). Thus, the normalcy of tridosha (bodily humours) is essential for maintaining the cognitive functions.

Diagnostic aspects of Alzheimer's disease as per Ayurveda

Depending on the lakshanas (signs and symptoms) exhibited by the patient, diagnosis should be done, the patient complaining of smritinasha (loss of memory), weakness in perception of subjects, and loss of concentration in daily activities due to nidana sevana (etiological factors) and other predisposing factors. AD falls under the category of jara (old age); it is swabavika

DRUGS USED TO IMPROVE MEMORY AND COGNITIVE FUNCTIONS

1) Brahmi (*Bacopa Monniera*).

In a clinical study on the effects of Brahmi (BM) on human memory, 76 adults aged between 40 and 65 years took part in a double blind randomized, placebo-controlled study in which various memory functions were tested and levels of anxiety measured. The results showed a significant effect of the BM on a test for the retention of new information. Follow-up tests showed that the rate of learning was unaffected, suggesting that BM decreases the rate of forgetting of newly acquired information.

Mandukaparni (*Centella Asiatica*)

In an experimental study, fresh centella asiatica plant extract was given orally to rat pups (n = 5), from P7-to P49 (6 weeks, 2 ml/kg/day). These and age-matched normal control (n = 5) rats were subjected to learning tests in the T-maze and the passive avoidance test. Following this, rats were sacrificed, and the amygdaloid nucleus was processed for Golgi staining. Results showed a significant increase in the percent correct response (control: 86.44 + 2.33% vs. Expt. 93.44 + 3.90%) in plant extract-treated rats. Passive avoidance retention test revealed a significant memory retention, and +dendritic intersection was significantly increased at

all concentric circles, except at 100 µm. Dendritic branching points also significantly increased in the inner three zones. These results indicate a correlation between improved learning capacity and increased dendritic arborisation in the amygdaloid nucleus. This may be the neural basis for enhanced learning in *C. asiatica*-treated rats.

Madhuyashti (*Glycyrrhiza Glabra*)

To investigate the effect of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* on learning and memory, the elevated plus-maze and passive avoidance paradigm were employed to evaluate learning and memory parameters. Three doses (75, 150, and 300 mg/kg p/o) of aqueous extract of *G. Glabra* were administered for 7 successive days in separate groups of mice. The dose of 150 mg/kg of the aqueous extract of liquorice significantly improved learning and memory of mice. Furthermore, this dose reversed the amnesia induced by diazepam 1 mg/kg i.p., scopolamine (0.4 mg/kg i.p.), and ethanol (1 mg/kg i.p.)

Shankhapushpi (*Convolvulus Pluricaulis*)

Shankhapushpi (*C.pluricaulis*) induces an increase in brain protein content, thus increasing acquisition efficiency.

Jatamansi (*Nordostachys Jatamansi*)

Rats were fed with *N. Jatamansi* for 15 days resulted significant increase in the levels of NE, DA, 5-HT, 5-HIAA and GABA. These data indicate that the alcoholic extract of the roots of *N. Jatamansi* causes an overall increase in the levels of central monoamines and inhibitory amino acids.

Ashwagandha (*Withania Somnifera*)

In an experimental study, daily administration of Ashwagandha root extract (50, 100, and 200 mg/kg orally) for 6 days significantly improved memory-consolidation in mice receiving chronic electroconvulsive shock (ECS) treatment. Ashwagandha administered on day 7 also attenuated the disruption of memory consolidation produced by chronic treatment with ECS. On the elevated plus maze, Ashwagandha reversed the scopolamine (0.3 mg/kg) induced delay in transfer latency on day 1. Based on these findings, it is suggested that Ashwagandha exhibits a nootropic-like effect in naive and amnesic mice.

Guduchi (*Tinospora Cordifolia*)

An experimental study was undertaken to study the effect of *T. cordifolia* (Tc) on learning and memory in normal rats and on cyclosporine-induced memory deficits. Both alcoholic and aqueous extract of *T. cordifolia* enhanced cognition in normal rats, as seen in behavioral tests-, Hebb William maze, and the passive avoidance task.

Jyotismati (*Celastrus Paniculatus*)

Ethanol extract of *C. paniculatus* was administered at the rate of 2 g/kg body weight orally 16 days before the trial

experiment in male Wister albino rats of 3, 12, and 20 months old animals. They were studied for learning and memory processes as well as for any change in the serum biochemistry. All animals were trained on Y-maze. Each animal received a daily session of 10 trials for 5 days, i.e., a maximum of 50 trials. Increase in response of the 5th session as compared to the 1st session was taken as criteria of learning and memory. There was a significant increase in learning and memory in the treated group with respect to its control. Results showed that *C. paniculatus* preferentially affects learning and recall of memory, and also regulates the serum biochemistry.

DISCUSSION

Medhyarasayana is extensively used for the ailments of mental and cognitive disorders. The four Medhya Rasayana, viz., Mandukaparni (*Centella asiatica*), Shankhapushpi (*Convolvulus pluricaulis*), Madhuyashti (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*), and Guduchi (*Tinospora cordifolia*) are especially mentioned as intellect-promoting drugs. The mode of action of Rasayana drugs and their benefits were discussed in the present article.

Why Rasayana?

Rasayana is considered an appropriate choice because of the following facts: It corrects the structural deformity of the Dhatus (tissues), thereby normalizing their functions.

Drugs helping in learning and memory Rasayana oushadhas do not have a common rasa (taste), veerya (potency), or guna (qualities), but all are deepana (appetizers) and Srotosodhana (cleans the channels). Normal functioning of srotas (channels) depends on healthy dhatus (tissues). Sroto soushtava (normalcy of dhatus) is highly essential to convey the nutrients to each and every cell. Shodhana (purificatory therapies) therapy acts at the level of doshas (humours), but rasayana drugs act still deeper, that is, at the level of dhatus (tissues). Hence, in deep-seated disease where severe vitiation of dhatus (tissues) occurs, such as AD, rasayana chikitsa is the regimen of choice.

AD is classified as a neurodegenerative disorder. The cause and progression of the disease are not well understood; it is associated with plaques and tangles in the brain. Current treatments only help with the symptoms of the disease. According to Ayurveda, learning is a result of successive and complex interaction and coordination of Indriyas (cognitive and motor organs), Indriyarthas (sense organs), Mana (psyche), Atma, and Buddhi (intellect). Drugs mentioned as Medhya (intellect-promoting) and those indicated to improve cognitive functions can be used successfully in cases of AD. The review indicates that Ayurvedic drugs like Brahmi, Mandookaparni, Shankhapushpi, Jyotishmati, Ashwagandha, Jatamansi, Madhuyashti, and Guduchi have the potential to provide a significant improvement in the memory and learning capacity of the elderly suffering from AD. All these drugs improve the brain functions and also the sensory and motor systems

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